

Law and Ethics : An Evaluatory Study

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1. Introduction

There are three areas of law where study on ethics has yielded fruitful results. To begin with, there are many similarities between the academic field of ethics and law, as well as between the subject matter of ethics and the field of law itself. The two fields have the characteristics of being multidisciplinary, normative, argumentative, and hermeneutic. Second, the fields share many core ideas, like democracy, human rights, and justice, and there is substantial overlap between them. Third, discussions of ethics and moral principles are commonplace in the legal profession since it is a normatively open activity. Ethical considerations are necessary for legal scholars and practitioners who want to investigate the boundaries of the right to privacy and the actions that a "reasonable man" would be required to take. Consequently, ethics and legal studies are like a brother and sister: very comparable and closely connected fields.

There are a lot of research on ethics and law in the scholarly literature. Does the existence of law need some kind of moral argument or standard? Are morality and the law incompatible? Should the state mandate moral behavior? Is it our moral duty to follow the rules? Such topics are common in legal philosophy, and there is no shortage of research that draws from both fields. Ethics and law in topics including abortion, euthanasia, animal biotechnology, and information and communication technologies have been the subject of several edited books. It could seem natural for a researcher of law to apply ethical ideas, and vice versa, due to the similarities in the fields and the usage of comparable language. It is astonishing, nevertheless, that the methodological concerns and the disciplines themselves have received so little attention. How can we tell the different fields apart? Would it be appropriate for legal academics to use the

same citation style for ethical treatises as they would for legal textbooks? When analyzing privacy laws, how might academics take ethical ideas into account?

This insufficient contemplation results in simplistic perspectives on the opposite field or topic in several investigations. It is common for ethicists to miss the mark when it comes to seeing law for what it is: both an authoritative structure and an argumentation activity that places a premium on sound normative reasoning. As a result, people tend to adopt one of two simplistic perspectives on law: one is a naïve positivist view, which reduces law to formal rules and authoritative rulings, while the other is a naïve idealist view, which reduces law to its argumentation aspect and treats it as similar to morality. We may all agree that murder is bad, but we have valid disagreements about how to evaluate euthanasia from a moral standpoint. This is an example of how many attorneys miss the mark when it comes to morality. So, it's possible to come across simplistic relativistic views in legal treatises (such as referring to "the" standards of professional ethics as if they can be found by reading influential texts) or simplistic positivist views (such as stating that all moral opinions are inherently subjective and that law should not be concerned with such opinions).

It is easy to be misled by the superficial parallels between the fields of morality and law. The first thing to remember while performing research that crosses traditional boundaries is to not assume, without more evidence, that one field is fundamentally related to another. When attorneys and ethicists use the same terminology, they often mean rather different things when they discuss privacy and autonomy. However, the reason interdisciplinary study is likely to be fruitful and stimulating is that the two fields have many similarities but are not identical.

This article presents the viewpoint of legal scholars who have a background in the law and who maintain an objective yet introspective stance towards the practice of law. Going beyond the letter of the law is essential due to the transparency of the law, yet the legal viewpoint continues to predominate. This is what I'm going to refer to as "interdisciplinary legal research," which is essentially bringing together experts from different fields to conduct a public legal research project with a primary focus on the

law. So, I won't go into details of how ethics fits into the field of law, or how legal historians and sociologists may benefit from working with ethics.

Since multidisciplinary studies often include teams of academics from different academic backgrounds, I will be focusing on research initiatives rather than specific individuals. I am curious as to how the incorporation of ethics into legal studies might enhance and enrich the field. How individual legal scholars could gain from engaging in multidisciplinary research is an alternative topic. As individuals gain familiarity with many points of view and are able to shift between them, they may develop a more critical understanding of the field's strengths and weaknesses, as well as acquire new skills and insights. All of this may be helpful when scholars go back to doing legal research from a single discipline. These formative impacts of multidisciplinary research are significant, but they are beyond the scope of this piece.

A basic overview of ethics (Section 2) is a good place to start when talking about ethical considerations in legal research. Section 3 devotes special attention to the quest for justification as a big ethical challenge. Accordingly, I will go over the parallels and contrasts between the fields of law and morality, as well as the two areas' interdependence (Section 4). Section 5 of the article provides an overview of five different kinds of ethically-based multidisciplinary legal research.

2. What is Ethics?

The study of right and wrong in a methodical way is known as ethics. It is often thought of as a synonym for moral philosophy when used as a term for a field of study. But "ethics" covers more ground. Theological ethics and moral theology are subfields of ethics, and there are non-philosophical varieties of descriptive ethics that draw from fields like sociology and psychology. An additional layer of ambiguity arises from the fact that "ethics" may mean both morality and the ethos of a particular group; for instance, "professional ethics" might mean either "law and ethics" or "legal ethics," the set of principles that govern the conduct of attorneys and other legal professionals. "Ethics" shall be defined in this article as the study of right and wrong conduct in society.

There are typically four subfields within ethics that are covered in introductory texts:

1. Moral Principles
2. Practicing Morality
3. Systemic ethics
4. Ethics that describes

Here I'll provide an overview of the four subfields of legal studies and explain how they could complement one another in cross-disciplinary studies.

1. At its heart lies the field of normative ethics. Normative theory-building and -criticism include the study of moral principles, values, and virtues.

Tolerance, paternalism, and autonomy are some of the more narrowly focused philosophies; others address more general topics like justice and fairness.

Normative ideas are varied and sometimes at odds with one another. There is a fundamental difference between deontological theories, which assert that certain types of actions are good or bad in and of themselves, and consequentialist theories, which determine the morality of an action according to its outcomes. While consequentialists consider the net benefit against any potential harm, deontologists hold that torture is always evil.

At this time, the most prominent theory in deontology is Kantianism. "Act only on the maxim through which you can at the same time will that it be a universal law," states the renowned Categorical Imperative, which is derived from Immanuel Kant's construction of a universal law that centers on man as a rational entity. The core concept is that we may evaluate moral laws by asking whether they can consistently be universalized. There are numerous somewhat different variants of this sophisticated notion, which is also found in Kant's work.

Utilitarianism, the dominant consequentialist theory, posits that we should strive to maximize the usefulness of our activities, as stated in the principle of utility. Many schools of utilitarianism disagree on whether the concept should be applied to specific actions or to general principles or norms, and on what exactly should be considered as utility—happiness, pleasure, or another more nuanced measure.

Normative ethics has been trending toward a more contextual and relational focus in recent decades, away from abstractions. People often say that abstract theories are flawed because they demand that we disregard the unique bonds we have with loved ones, even yet these bonds play a significant role in our moral experience. As an example, feminists have said that our attention would be better served by concentrating on real men and women, complete with unique life experiences and meaningful connections to loved ones, rather than on gender-neutral abstractions. Neo-Aristotelians, who reject consequentialism and deontology in favor of virtue ethics that places an emphasis on an individual's character, have made similar arguments.

A broad outline of the present arguments in normative ethics is all that these comments can provide. It is prudent to adopt a pluralist attitude and acknowledge that these opposing discourses may each provide significant insights to the environment of legal interdisciplinary study. It could be beneficial for a legal researcher interested in justice to explore many theories to find the one that works best for their research assignment. To stay out of hot water in the field of normative ethics, a legal researcher shouldn't choose a side. This comment is relevant to every branch of ethics, in fact. A legal scholar may not be able to provide a good enough explanation for her theory choice if she isn't an expert in the arguments herself.

Integrating normative ethics into multidisciplinary legal study requires sufficient prudence due to the intrinsically contentious character of the field. Prior work on concepts such as autonomy, respect, tolerance, fairness, or privacy may serve as a springboard for further investigation into relevant areas of law. Also, if you have a hermeneutic view of law as Ronald Dworkin does, you may be able to integrate it directly into your legal interpretation of positive law since law is an open system. An

equitable income tax or social security system, for instance, or how to strike a balance between religious freedom and free speech in contentious cases like the Danish cartoons depicting Mohamed are all examples of areas where normative ethics may provide light.

2. Several subfields fall under the umbrella term "applied ethics," and they address real-world problems including abortion, corruption, and animal biotechnology.

Biomedical ethics, animal ethics, corporate ethics, and legal ethics are areas that have seen a lot of research and development. Still in their infancy are fields like international ethics and sports ethics.

It was in the 1960s that the field of applied ethics began to take shape. At first, many philosophers viewed applied ethics as if it were as simple as applying broad ideas of morality. This was too easy, they quickly realized. Research into emerging topics like genetic testing and animal biotechnology has cast doubt on long-held normative frameworks, which either failed to address these novel questions or offered solutions that appeared inherently wrong. Animal integrity and data privacy are two new ideas that developed in these areas. There used to be one-way application between applied and normative ethics, but now there is a two-way dialectical interaction.

There is a difference in the breadth and amount of generality between normative and applied ethics, but this is not the same thing as a difference in quality. Theoretical and normative work in normative ethics may be evaluated and understood in relation to their interpretation and reconstruction in many areas of practical ethics; yet, these norms and ideas are relevant across many domains. In order for normative ethics to progress, practical ethics must provide input, and vice versa.

Since attorneys tend to concentrate on particular areas of law, like health law or business law, rather than broad ideas of justice, applied ethics may be a great resource for multidisciplinary studies of law. Therefore, the related area of applied ethics is the obvious choice for research partners in ethics. Institutionalizing such multidisciplinary collaboration is common; for instance, health law and bioethics institutions regularly work together.

3. Meta-ethics is philosophical contemplation on the field of ethics as a whole, including its foundational ideas, assumptions, and methodologies. Moral judgments and the assignment of blame are among the topics covered. Some of the questions it poses include: Is it possible to be held accountable for what we do while drunk? Is there any truth to moral claims, or are they just personal preferences? Ideas like morality, rights, and autonomy—what do they mean?

It is possible to examine the meaning of a term like autonomy without taking a position on the value of autonomy, according to many philosophers who hold the view that meta-ethics is a normatively neutral field. Some people, including the author, think that meta-ethics can't be fully realized until we link it with normative ethics; otherwise, analyzing ideas or procedures in isolation from ethics has little use. Positivists and non-positivists engage in a comparable argument in legal philosophy, for example, over ideas like *mens rea*.

Research in the field of law may benefit from meta-ethics in a number of ways. Researchers in the field of law may benefit from meta-ethical examinations of moral ideas like intention, autonomy, privacy, and rights in order to better understand the related legal notions. Furthermore, court cases are often cited by ethicists who study responsibility, if for no other reason than the detailed accounts they provide. It is possible that analogous debates in ethics may enrich the newly developing field of legal methodology. For instance, the widespread philosophical discussion around the reflective equilibrium method—discussed in Section 3—could serve as a source of inspiration for contemplations on legal research—since it has many similarities with legal reasoning.

4. A branch of ethics known as descriptive ethics draws on fields like sociology, psychology, and biology to provide a detailed account of moral theory and practice. The views of doctors and other medical professionals on euthanasia might be described by a sociologist. There should be no normative stance taken by the impartial observer on these beliefs and activities. It makes no difference whether he supports them or is very critical of them. Because of the effect of one's own opinions and implicit assumptions

on one's perceptions, this is not a simple task. Some possible strategies for minimizing this kind of bias include doing research in the field alongside someone who has different normative beliefs, or soliciting feedback on the preliminary description from both within and outside the researched group.

Economics is one of the first fields to include ethical considerations. Adam Smith, one of the fathers of modern economics, also wrote voluminously on matters of morality and ethics. Ethicists have been debating the validity of their normative theories since the 1950s by drawing on ideas from allied fields such as rational choice theory and game theory. Psychology is another field that is seeing more and more integration with moral philosophy. Normative theories shouldn't demand the impossible from humans, and the insights from psychology may provide a critical view on what is reasonable to expect from people. It is experimentally untenable to assume that people make completely logical decisions since moral psychologists have shown how unconscious processes impact our behaviors. Many rationalist ethical views, including Kantianism, are challenged from this vantage point.

Descriptive ethics, according to traditional definitions, belongs to the biological or social sciences and not moral philosophy. Normative philosophical analysis incorporates empirical insights, and vice versa; social science research questions are partly determined by normative problems; however, interdisciplinary cooperation among philosophers and other scholars has grown increasingly common in recent decades. Commonly referred to as "empirical ethics," this method combines normative and descriptive components.

More and more people are interested in pragmatism and hermeneutical philosophy, which is typically associated with this shift towards empirical ethics. In these worldviews, truth and value are inseparable; rather, we can only make sense of social behaviors by examining the values and standards they represent. So, it's clear that a social science based on positivism cannot exist.

In multidisciplinary legal research, descriptive ethics—and empirical ethics in particular—can be important in a number of ways. If we want to control a practice, for

example, they may provide light on its intrinsic normativity, which is crucial for doing so effectively. Open legal standards and ideas that alludes to morality, whether directly or indirectly, including reasonableness, fairness, and the standard of good care, may be better understood with the help of descriptive and empirical ethics. Which school of thought—descriptive ethics' emphasis on positive social morality or normative ethics' emphasis on reflective critical morality—should have the last say in interpreting these standards is contentious among legal philosophers. References to public morality may be significant in understanding the law, especially in Common Law systems where law is typically seen as the embodiment of morality. Thus, comparative studies in legal culture must include comparative moral sociology.

Rather of drawing clear borders between them, writers often draw from all four of these subfields. Consider the seminal work *A Theory of Justice* by John Rawls (Rawls 1971). In this work, he lays out a framework for civil disobedience (applied ethics) that is consistent with his philosophy of justice (normative ethics). There is no more seminal work on each subject than his book. In addition to his work in moral psychology and rational choice, his contributions to meta-ethics include the reflective equilibrium approach, the concept of a social contract, and other related ideas.

There are a lot of fields that are strongly linked to ethics; sometimes, the boundaries between them are blurry. This is particularly the case in the fields of law and political philosophy. The fact that courses in all three fields often examine the same book by Rawls is indicative of the strong relationship between them. The emphasis of political philosophy is on political institutions like the state or democracy, while the focus of ethics is on the acts of people and organizations. This difference is useful but somewhat arbitrary. Thus, the branch of study concerned with the foundations of law is known as legal philosophy. Discipline is defined by the dominant viewpoint, not the problem itself. For instance, we may look at civil disobedience through the lenses of all three fields. Philosophers in the fields of ethics, politics, and law have investigated the question of when citizens have a duty to follow the law, how democracies should respond to civil disobedience, and whether or not legal systems can account for the

unique nature of civil disobedience when deciding on punishments. These analyses are obviously connected and make reference to one another, yet they are also distinct.

3. The search for justification

Justifying normative theories and judgments is one of the central topics of meta-ethics. Systematic observation and controlled experimentation are two examples of the procedures used in most scientific fields. These approaches provide data that may be used to develop ideas. Law school libraries include reams of statutory language and judicial precedent upon which the development of legal concepts might be based. Yet, neither a commonly acknowledged technique nor a reasonably definite foundation are present in normative ethics. From what I've seen, a lot of law students fail to take ethics seriously because they see moral judgments as nothing more than personal preferences. Consequently, we should talk in length about this matter here.

The likelihood of ethics coming to a consensus on ideas, techniques, and judgments may seem low. It may seem as if new ethical ideas are introduced every century, but in reality, the diverse ethical traditions have been quarreling for eons, and moral plurality and ethical pluralism are equally present in our everyday lives. Consequently, ethics and morality may seem to be completely subjective, a question of individual preference.

This skeptical or subjectivist stance is actually defended by certain ethicists. This extreme pessimism is, in my opinion, both unneeded and unjustified. When it comes to the fundamental standards, there is a lot of agreement on many topics (murder, theft, etc.). We are generally in accord, yet we may have minor disagreements on tangential matters like the death penalty and unlawful music copying. My conviction that it is immoral to murder an innocent guy for no good reason is as rock solid as my opinion that the sun is at the center of the universe. Some of our moral beliefs are well-grounded. Case in point: no major theory of ethics upholds the morality of stealing or murder, despite the many debates over its bases and justifications. Which leads us to believe that reasonable consensus and reasonable pluralism coexist.

In terms of approach, it's possible the same holds true. Several tools from the fields of philosophy and social science are available to the study of ethics. It is capable of using philosophical approaches to conceptual analysis, testing the consistency of ideas, and putting arguments to the test via logic. By drawing on findings in philosophical history, it is possible to comprehend the defense and critique of normative arguments across history. It could also include research that look at the influence of moral codes as well as popular morality and moral behaviors. These techniques aren't a panacea for justification, but they may assist eliminate the most blatantly flawed arguments and hypotheses. While these approaches may not always provide definitive results, they have the potential to strengthen our assertions and deserve further investigation.

Two facts—acceptable moral plurality and reasonable moral consensus—should be the foundation of any sound examination of ethical reasoning. On certain matters, we are unsure of our position or acknowledge that reasonable people may have different opinions; on other others, we cannot help but think that every reasonable person should embrace our perspective. Even the most contentious positions lack an absolute basis in ethics, much alone the latter. The more disputed viewpoints, as well as the more intuitively appealing ones, may be examined and their dependability increased in this way.

There are three main schools of thought when it comes to providing evidence for moral convictions. One, known as foundationalism, seeks indisputable premises upon which to construct a theory of normative behavior. The second, known as abstract constructivism, is to provide a general theoretical explanation that may underpin normative ethical theories by removing ourselves from specific contexts, biases, and personal interests. The third one involves reconstructing our common ideals and concrete intuitions critically; it is primarily linked to the hermeneutic and pragmatic traditions.

The approach based on foundationalism has historically predominated. It was believed that the most basic source of moral truth came from divine revelation, either directly in the Torah, the Bible, or the Qur'an, or indirectly via prophets and priests. It remains so for a large number of believers, particularly among more conservative branches of Islam

and Christianity. Nonetheless, it fails to provide a universally acceptable foundation for morality in view of the religious heterogeneity prevalent in contemporary society. The majority of religious writings also avoid discussing the many ethical dilemmas brought forth by technological advancements. For this reason, Reason has become a trusted source for many writers seeking to establish right and wrong. Philosophers like Plato and Kant have contended that reason may enlighten us about right and wrong. But not even a tiny fraction of the intellectual community has been swayed by their (and subsequent generations') proposals for what this might include.

Regardless of the foundationalism version, there are two main arguments against it. The most basic is that they don't provide out a silver bullet for arriving at universally acceptable normative findings. Second, even if we accept the very abstract basis, it is very difficult—if not impossible—to derive precise moral judgments on matters like genetic modification or euthanasia. Typically, arguments for and against a given topic are based on these abstract underpinnings, making these ideas seem to lack practical significance.

The second approach is constructivism, which involves separating one's interests and prejudices from one's research via the use of hypothetical mental models. The social contract is a famous piece of architecture that asks, "What would people in a wild setting agree on if they had to arrange for peaceful cooperation?" The concept of a state of nature is used by some writers, while others propose spaceships or groups on deserted islands after a shipwreck. John Rawls's (1971) "original position" is the most important construction. He puts us in a situation where we may pretend to sign a social compact while remaining completely ignorant of the details. It doesn't matter whether we're gifted or disabled; what matters is that we don't know who we are. As a result, we need to establish principles that would be acceptable to everyone in this unpredictable circumstance, rather than tailoring the contract to our own requirements. In his view, the most well-founded principles are those on which we would reach a consensus in this kind of circumstance. It is a relative justification, not an assertion of ultimate truth, that he makes.

As a result of using such theoretical frameworks, we may be able to increase the argument's dependability by removing most subjective biases. Unfortunately, our real ideas and behaviors do not align with the approach or the outcomes. In a scenario as implausible as this, why should we let ourselves be led by consensus-based principles? Because I am not that idealized version of myself that lacks the details that make me unique, I see no reason to feel obligated to adhere to those values. Given the prevalence of violent crime, social unrest, war, and terrorism in today's world, how effective would a nonviolent philosophy be in a utopian society?

More weight is given to context in the third method. Our practical intuitions and habits serve as the foundation. We must not assume that our present moral beliefs and actions are free from the influence of biases such as egocentrism, bigotry, and a lack of empathy. However, instead of letting go of our existing beliefs entirely, as in the first two methods, we should seek to critically update them so that we may build moral theories and principles that we can genuinely adhere to. This is the common ground between hermeneutical philosophy and pragmatism, despite the fact that they are from distinct schools of thought.

Personally, I find John Rawls's proposal for a reflective equilibrium process to be the most intriguing. We begin with our reasonably certain moral intuitions. We next combine these factors with others, including overarching concepts and theoretical frameworks about human nature and society at large. General principles, insights from sociology and psychology, and hard data about our society are just a few of the other components that we may include. It is recommended that all pertinent details be included in the mixture. However, at first, the theory is essentially nonsensical when we attempt to integrate these disparate pieces into it. Consequently, we need to make adjustments to them via a dialectical process; for example, we need to validate some of our intuitions since they turned out to be wrong, modify certain principles because they don't align with our strongly held intuitions or with sociological findings about the feasibility of social cooperation, etc. We will have a moral theory that is justified when we achieve a state of equilibrium in which all components are coherent. To attorneys, this method may even appear instinctive since it is comparable to, and maybe even

inspired by, the way lawyers build legal doctrines, where case law serves as moral intuitions.

This method has the benefit of being open to all pertinent data while nevertheless beginning with our own beliefs. I think it's more practical. This dynamic potential is further enhanced by the fact that fresh information has the ability to shake things up and make us reevaluate our ethical stances. But the issue with this strategy is that we can't help but be biased and prejudiced in some way. Just like the other two ways, this one has its pros and cons. Because they are not rooted in particular cultures, the first two techniques may be less impacted by prejudice; nonetheless, they may not be acceptable as action guides for actual humans coping with complicated circumstances due to their generality and abstraction. Both hermeneutic and pragmatic approaches have the potential to systematize bias even as they lead to more applicable and palatable explanations. Thus, what is known as triangulation in the social sciences is the use of many methodologies in conjunction to arrive at the optimum solution. We could be more confident in our decision-making abilities if they all point in the same way.

4. Similarities and Differences and the Intertwinement of Law and Morality

Both the study of law and morality, as well as the fields that focus on both, have many similarities. Starting with a comparison of the topics is necessary since the most significant similarities and contrasts across the disciplines are all connected to them.

To direct human behavior, we have hermeneutic, normative, and argumentative systems and practices in the form of law and morality. The use of argument is fundamental in both fields; in fact, law has been defined as an argumentative activity by many legal theorists, most notably Ronald Dworkin (Dworkin 1978). Plus, they're both essentially social policies that aim to improve our lives and the lives of others around us by regulating certain behaviors.

Still, it's not always simple to tell where ethics and law diverge. Since there are always exceptions, it seems that no matter how hard you try to establish a unique criteria, you will always fail (Shklar 1964). Although several criteria have been proposed, none of

them are applicable in every situation. There will always be instances of law or moral principles that don't add up. Some criteria have been proposed, such as the idea that law is synonymous with sanctions (which would render most international and soft law null and void), sovereignty (which is problematic due to customary and international law), or the control of outward behavior, as opposed to the internal, intentional side of behavior, as shown by morality (which is problematic due to utilitarianism in morality and mens rea in law). A uniform criteria for differentiation, let alone separation, between law and morality cannot be found in these traits, despite their association with law and the fact that they are necessary for understanding the majority of laws (Van der Burg 2009).

Legal authority and authoritative methods for recognizing, interpreting, and implementing legal standards and for altering them are present in a fully evolved legal system, which is connected with most of the mentioned differences. Secondary rules of recognition, adjudication, and modification are defined by H.L.A. Hart (1961). But many rules in the law may be argued for or against on moral grounds (Dworkin 1978). Integral to such a free system is the concept of morality. Thus, although secondary rules may be beneficial for identifying legal systems, they will not be able to differentiate law from morality or even assist identify legal systems.

When it comes to ethics, it's important to make a similar argument. Differentiating morality from other, comparable organizations like law or etiquette is challenging because of the lack of universally applicable standards. There are four possible criteria in the literature, however they are all not applicable in every situation.

The following are some of the claims made by morality and law: first, that morality is supremely authoritative; second, that morality is normative or prescriptive; third, that moral statements should be universalisable, meaning they apply to everyone in similar situations; fourth, that morality should consider the good of others; however, not all elements of morality are normative in this sense; for example, we can assign blame or responsibility. The four criteria may all be helpful in understanding morality, but none of them is a necessary condition of morality (or a distinguishing criterion), according to Beauchamp (1993).

Not only does the legal system have an intrinsic distinctiveness, but so do the views of attorneys and legal experts. When compared to ethicists, attorneys have a different work culture. When arguing, lawyers often employ jargon and technical terms that the average person wouldn't dream of using. It is important to note that just because two fields use identical terminology or approach comparable problems in their work does not guarantee that they are really working on the same issue. Both the approaches and the language used are influenced by the professional attitudes and institutional setting.

The perspective on those in positions of power is fundamentally different. A vast corpus of authoritative writings is comprised of judicial and legislative judgments and norms, even if not all law is established by these bodies. Nowhere in ethics is such submission to power exemplified. While there may be writers with considerable sway, such sway is contingent upon the quality of their arguments and analysis. Legal professionals also vary in that they are educated to prioritize process. Ethicists are not wholly unfamiliar with ideas like procedural fairness, but they do not hold them in the same esteem as they do in legal theory. One similarity is that law seeks to resolve disputes via finality. The goal of implementing legal processes is to simplify the dispute by limiting its scope, neutralizing its effects, and finally ending it. Many attorneys have adopted this mindset of peaceful resolution, although ethicists often see it as the inverse. No end in sight is possible for philosophical debates; they may go on indefinitely until one side gives up or dies. An overwhelming majority of philosophers seem to operate on the premise that more complexity, hypothetical examples, and pertinent aspects are always welcome. To put it too simply: seeing a lawyer may make the issue seem easier as they have concentrated on the most important parts of the case; seeing a philosopher, on the other hand, will make the problem seem even more complicated.

Similar variations in attitude and style may be seen if we shift our focus from the topics to the academic specialties. When it comes to authority, process, and closure, ethicists don't follow the same pattern as lawyers. However, being hermeneutic, argumentative, and normative, the fields have many similarities. Since of their inclusive nature and focus on the ethical and legal aspects of social phenomena, these fields are intrinsically

multidisciplinary since they draw on the knowledge of other fields to better understand these phenomena.

Given the rich variety of knowledge found within each academic field, it is possible that disagreements between experts in the same field can be less consequential than those within related fields. Researching law from a Dworkinian or natural law perspective may benefit more from collaborating with ethicists than positivist attorneys. An economics and law professor may look to utilitarianism for guidance, whereas a law and literature professor working side by side may find his job completely bewildering.

The findings indicate that there are only subtle and situational distinctions between the fields of ethics and law, as well as between the issues of morality and law. We can't say anything broad about them, but they do exist. Only in certain settings can we hope to get an understanding of them. Although many legal systems and moral codes have their own quirks, there are no universally applicable differences. The degree to which a particular legal culture allows for the incorporation of moral principles into the law varies from one legal culture to another (Taekema 2003).

Due to their partial intermingling, the fields of ethics and legal research are inseparable, and neither is the study of law and morality. Ethical considerations are inherent to the work of a legal scholar. Attempting to do so leaves her bewildered since she will inevitably miss certain aspects of the legislation. Researchers in the domains of health law and biotechnology law, for instance, need to be sensitive to the moral aspects of their subjects and adept at incorporating ethics into their work since these areas of law are still developing vigorously in close relationship with moral perspectives on those sectors.

A legal researcher is compelled to do multidisciplinary study that incorporates ethics due to the partial intertwining of law and morality. In contrast, he can't fall into the trap of treating this as if it were inherently monodisciplinary due to the law's relative autonomy, its uniqueness, and legal views. The potential and difficulty of interdisciplinary study stem from the fact that different fields are both interdependent and unique.

5. Five Ways to Combine Legal Research and Ethics

There are many ways in which legal studies and ethics might be integrated.

1. Ethics as Heuristics

The simplest kind of interdisciplinary study only incorporates the second field to provide fresh ideas and inspiration. Ethics may serve as a source of great inspiration for attorneys because of the many parallels to the law. Particularly in emerging areas of law with limited access to both written and intellectual materials, this will be the case. For instance, as a legal scholar, I have been able to evaluate the Dutch health law's heavy emphasis on autonomy through the lens of the ethics of care's original critique of liberal ethics' supremacy of justice and individual autonomy.

There can be no methodological orthodoxy since the main objective is to inspire creativity. As long as it provides fresh viewpoints, it doesn't matter whether the legal researcher has entirely misinterpreted the ethical texts or concepts he employs. When applied to the discovery context, this methodological anarchism's flip side is that ethics has no place in providing a rationale. A legal framework is necessary for testing and justifying the novel concept. Although it may be stated in a footnote, the fact that the author gained an idea from studying ethics is usually unimportant when presenting the research findings.

2. Ethics as an Auxiliary Discipline

Research in the legal field could benefit from information from an ancillary area. To illustrate the point, descriptive ethics has the potential to provide light on the perspectives of both patients and physicians as well as on the realities of euthanasia. Theories on the moral justification of euthanasia and other fundamental notions like "suffering" may be found in philosophical ethics.

Concepts like "standard of good care," "fairness," and "equity" are notoriously difficult for lawyers to pin down. A legal scholar may need to go beyond legal documents and

into ethics to ascertain the meaning of such words (and particularly to propose new interpretations).

To illustrate the point, the European Convention on Human Rights allows for the possibility of limiting most rights for the sake of public morality. Details on the moral stances held by a particular nation could be crucial for understanding these provisions. Researcher critical thinking skills are also required; moral convictions that are openly prejudiced cannot serve as a basis for sound legal reasoning. Therefore, it is essential for the legal researcher to have knowledge of constructive social morality and the ability to critically evaluate and rebuild.

Credible ethical insights are essential for legal study. Since this form of study is more stringent than its predecessor, it is imperative that all methodological standards relevant to ethics be upheld. For descriptive ethics to work, the social scientific community must agree on the methodologies employed to study people's beliefs and behaviors. In order for a legal researcher to employ philosophical ethics, they must provide well-grounded philosophical arguments and adhere to generally recognized philosophical methodologies.

3. Comparative Research

The third kind of legal research is to conduct two independent projects on the same topics using identical questions and methodologies; this will allow for the eventual merging of the two studies and the highlighting of their shared and unique aspects. This kind of study yields excellent results because of the close relationship between law and morality. Legal scholars will be able to reflect more critically on positive law because to the mirror that such comparisons provide, and they may discover new ways to conduct legal study thanks to the disparities that are uncovered. Studies that zeroed in on a particular problem (the embryo's moral and legal standing, for instance), argument structure (the slippery slope argument), methodology (reflective equilibrium), or set of concepts (ideals and principles) were the ones that succeeded in my personal experience when using a comparative viewpoint.

It is possible to classify this branch of comparative law as a third subfield of the field. It doesn't compare one area of law to another (like criminal law vs. tort law) or even to another country (like liability in the UK vs. the Netherlands), but rather to morals (like health law vs. bioethics). The fundamental issue with this form of comparative study is the same as with others: how can we compare things that are similar but not identical? To avoid making hasty assumptions based on a false sense of familiarity, researchers should take stock of their own disciplinary biases. It is crucial to modify and improve the research questions and methodologies used in both fields to enable comparability. Researchers conducting such comparisons must be well-versed in both fields, which often necessitates collaboration between ethicists and lawyers.

4. Dialectical Cooperation

Dialectical multidisciplinary research represents a more robust kind of integration. Despite being in different academic fields, the two initiatives interact with one other at various points. Because of this ongoing dialogue, scientists are able to fine-tune their studies. Think of a lawyer who is interested in reflective balance as a field of study. He may study ethical limitations on methodology and attempt to apply them to the law. On the other side, he may say that with this approach to law, something crucial would be missing. Ethicists often find that this prompts them to reevaluate their approach to the problem. Each professional is responsible for their own project, but both the ethicist and the lawyer are willing to hear each other out. This was the format used for an organ donation project in which I participated. When the legal and ethical discussions on consent (and particularly the role of family) met, we proceeded to make adjustments to our respective analyses until we felt that the interchange had enhanced both sides' perspectives to the fullest extent possible. When the law is very amenable to moral reasoning and both the problem and the sector are still evolving, such in the case of biotechnology or information and communication technology (ICT), this setup is particularly fruitful.

Improving disciplinary analysis and achieving a more complete knowledge with the addition of the mirror and more critical input from other viewpoints is the main goal of

such a dialectical undertaking. Ultimately, the disciplinary viewpoints do not combine; rather, it is the responsibility of the legal researcher to ascertain whether ethical considerations may be incorporated into the legal viewpoint and which cannot. Therefore, each field's methodological standards apply. The translation and transformation challenge is an important one. It is important to be mindful of the possibility of misconceptions when translating ethical assessments into legal categories and vice versa. This is due to the fact that lawyers and ethicists may give somewhat different meanings to the same terminology. Having someone on the team who is trained as both a lawyer and an ethicist is essential, in my opinion, for a project of this kind.

5. Integrated Research

One integrated research endeavor requires an all-encompassing viewpoint and is the most intense kind of collaboration. Typically, this viewpoint is based on the study question, which can ask: "Should the laws regarding X (for instance, equal treatment, organ transplants, or euthanasia) be altered and, if so, how exactly?" Typically, an interdisciplinary scholarly viewpoint or a policy viewpoint (focusing on what needs to be addressed) constitute the integrating perspective.

The reader's theoretical perspective determines whether complete integration is considered feasible. It is, according to some pragmatics. Even for philosophers who consider moral speech to be a subset of legal discourse, this is true. In my opinion, it is not feasible to have a completely integrated viewpoint. We should be cognizant that even while striving for complete integration, we will always encounter perspectives. Although it draws on many other fields' ideas, the new integrated method is only a different viewpoint; it will inevitably leave out some important details.

The editors make a valid point when they say that these five forms of multidisciplinary study may synergize with one another. The dynamics could work in either direction. From time to time, a small-scale collaboration grows into a larger-scale integrated initiative. Additionally, the researchers may find that an integrated viewpoint is too ambitious and end up settling for a comparative study instead. One word of warning:

don't put these kinds of investigations in a strict hierarchy. Depending on the goals of the study, different forms of transdisciplinary research may be more or less appropriate. Methodological considerations, benefits, and drawbacks are unique to each purpose and kind. Assuming these things are considered, I think legal scholars will often discover that incorporating ethics into their work is a very fulfilling and motivating experience.

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